

Filipino Leadership Styles of School Heads and Teachers' Commitment of Public Elementary Schools in Maa District

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Abstract. The study aimed to determine the extent of Filipino leadership styles of school heads and the extent of teachers' commitment of public elementary schools in Maa District. This study employed a non-experimental quantitative research design utilizing descriptive-correlation method. Validated questionnaire and Universal sampling procedure were utilized considering the minimal number of teachers in the research locale. One hundred ten (110) public elementary school teachers were the respondents of the study. Using mean, Pearson's r , and regression analysis, the findings revealed that the Filipino leadership styles of school heads was extensive while the extent of teachers' commitment of public elementary schools was also extensive. Moreover, the overall results disclosed that indicators for the Filipino leadership styles of school heads were positively correlated to the teachers' commitment of public elementary schools. Further, results from the regression analysis revealed the following have a strong influence of Filipino leadership styles of school heads on the teachers' commitment of public elementary schools: hard work, loophole, and connection. It is recommended that the Department of Education should design leadership training programs that emphasize Filipino cultural values and their role in strengthening teacher commitment. It is also recommended that school heads encouraged to strengthen participative and value-driven leadership practices that promote collaboration, trust, and shared responsibility among teachers.

KEY WORDS

1. Filipino leadership styles
2. Teachers' commitment
3. public elementary schools

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1. Introduction

Effective leadership role provided by the school head will lead to the achievement of the school's goals and objectives. Education among other concern is an instrument for effecting national development with the formulation of national policy on education. The school heads' leadership style in elementary schools is a pointer of the level of productivity of teachers or their job performance. Effective school head leadership strategies increase school organization, teaching, and student performance outcomes. The primary beneficiaries of the study are the school heads and teachers themselves. By examining how indigenous Filipino leadership practices such as pakikisama, bayanihan, and utang na loob influence teacher commitment, the study offers valuable insights that can help school leaders adopt more culturally responsive and effective management styles. Teachers, in turn, may benefit from lead-

ership that fosters a supportive, participatory, and motivating work environment, ultimately enhancing their commitment and job satisfaction. To address the growing need to understand how culturally embedded leadership practices influence teacher behavior and performance in the Philippine educational context. With Filipino values such as pakikisama, bayanihan, and malasakit shaping how school heads lead, it is essential to examine how these traits affect teachers' levels of commitment, particularly in public schools where challenges such as resource limitations and high workloads are common. In global studies have explored the diverse leadership styles of school heads and their impact on educational outcomes. A notable study by Soncin et al., (2024) analyzed data from the OECD's Teaching and Learning International Survey (TALIS) across 32 countries. The researchers identified four leadership profiles: integrating leaders (64.9%), who combine instructional and distributed leadership; participative leaders (22.2%), who emphasize distributed leadership; supportive leaders (8.5%), focusing on instructional leadership; and contingent leaders (4.4%), who lack a specific leadership approach. Yue (2024) focused on a university in Beijing, China, exploring how different leadership styles of school leaders impact teachers' mental health. The qualitative research revealed that collaborative and supportive leadership styles are linked to positive mental health outcomes among teachers, while authoritarian and directive styles contribute to stress and dissatisfaction. The study recommends implementing leadership development initiatives, transparent communication channels, and strategies to alleviate workload pressures to promote teacher well-being. Teaching in public elementary schools presents numerous challenges that contribute to stress among teachers. Stress among teachers is a growing concern globally, affecting not only their health but also their professional performance. Kaufman et al., (2023) examined the prevalence of stress among teachers across 25 countries and identified key stressors such as workload, learner behavior, and lack of professional support. In the Philippines, Ramirez and Capili (2024) examined the relationship between school heads' leadership styles and teacher retention in Tuguegarao City. Their findings indicate that transactional leadership is prevalent, with significant associations between leadership style and factors such as work environment, job satisfaction, and teacher morale. In Eastern Samar, Anabo and Rapada Jr. (2024) explored the relationship between various leadership styles and teacher performance. They discovered that while transformational, transactional, authoritative, and laissez-faire styles were evident, transactional leadership negatively impacted teacher performance. This suggests a need for school heads to balance different leadership approaches to optimize teacher outcomes. Further, Francisco (2024) examined paternalistic leadership in Philippine basic education institutions. The study highlighted that morality-based and benevolent leadership positively affected organizational outcomes, while authoritarian leadership had a lesser impact. In the context of Maa District, where diverse challenges in education persist, the ability of school leaders to inspire, motivate, and support their teachers directly impacts their dedication to teaching and learner success. A strong commitment among teachers leads to higher job satisfaction, improved instructional quality, and better learner outcomes. This study aims to explore how the Filipino leadership styles of school heads' in Maa District influence teachers' commitment, providing insights that can enhance leadership practices and strengthen the educational system in the district. This study on Filipino leadership styles among school heads and its impact on teacher commitment in Maa District's public elementary schools is highly relevant to both national educational goals and local community development. Nationally, un-

derstanding effective leadership is crucial for improving educational outcomes, fostering a positive school culture, and ensuring the successful implementation of curriculum reforms like MATATAG, which heavily rely on committed teachers. Locally, in Maa District, the research provides valuable insights into how specific leadership approaches can either enhance or hinder teacher morale, professional growth, and dedication, directly affecting the quality of education delivered to the community's children. By identifying leadership practices that cultivate strong teacher commitment, the study offers a pathway to strengthen the educational backbone of the district, ultimately benefiting students, parents, and the entire community.

1.1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework of the Study—This study is anchored on the Kapwa Theory of Virgilio Enriquez (1992), which emphasizes shared identity, empathy, and relational harmony as core principles of Filipino social interaction and leadership. In the context of school leadership, Kapwa shapes how school heads relate to teachers promoting a leadership style that is participatory, compassionate, and culturally sensitive. Filipino values such as pakikipagkapwa, pakikisama, and utang na loob influence school leaders to build trust, show concern, and maintain strong interpersonal bonds, which are essential in fostering a committed teaching workforce. In addition, the framework draws from Paternalistic-Authoritarian Leadership Theory (Jocano, 1999), which is characterized by leaders acting as parental figures who

provide direction while offering emotional support and protection. This leadership style, while hierarchical, is also nurturing and responsive to the needs of subordinates. Teacher commitment, in this study, is conceptualized using Meyer and Allen's (1991) Three-Component Model of Commitment, which includes affective commitment (emotional attachment), continuance commitment (perceived cost of leaving), and normative commitment (moral obligation to stay). The assumption is that culturally aligned leadership styles among Filipino school heads rooted in relational and value-based interactions can enhance teachers' commitment in all three dimensions. The conceptual framework posits that the Filipino leadership styles of school heads (independent variable), which are influenced by indigenous and paternalistic leadership values, have a significant effect on the level of commitment of public elementary school teachers (dependent variable) in Maa District. This relationship is expected to be mediated by cultural dynamics and organizational context, where values of trust, empathy, and loyalty play a central role. Presented in Figure 1 is the theoretical and conceptual framework of study where the Filipino leadership styles of school heads with the indicators of independent variable namely: hard work, loophole and connection and the dependent variable is teachers' commitment which include affective commitment, countenance commitment, and normative commitment of public elementary school teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City.

2. Methodology

This chapter outlines the research methods that guide the conduct of this study. It presents the research design, the respondents involved, the research instrument, and the procedures for data collection

2.1. Research Design—This research utilized a non-experimental quantitative research design with a correlational approach. Accord-

ing to Dela Cruz et al. (2024), the descriptive-correlational method was used to assess the relationship between two or more variables and

Fig. 1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

determine the degree of their association. Additionally, Velasco and Ramos (2023) emphasized that the method was applicable in studies that sought to describe personal attributes and clarify the characteristics of the data. In this regard, the research is descriptive in that it aims to evaluate school heads' Filipino leadership styles and teachers' commitment in public elementary schools in Maa District, Division of Davao City. It is correlational, for it purposes to find out if there is a significant relationship between the leadership styles exercised by school heads and the teachers' commitment.

2.2. Ethical Consideration—Established research protocols and ethical guidelines were strictly followed, particularly in managing population data with utmost confidentiality and care. The survey questionnaire was prepared and submitted, supported by relevant scholarly references, for thorough evaluation and validation. Upon receiving approval from the Ethics Committee, the data collection phase of the study

was undertaken.

2.3. Research Respondents—This study focused on Grade 4 to 5 public school teachers in Maa District with 3-6 years of DepEd experience during SY 2024–2025, who were at a critical career stage as they adapted to the MATATAG Curriculum while navigating classroom realities. Following DepEd Memorandum No. 32, s. 2020, which provided guidelines for equitable representation, the sample size was calculated using Slovin's formula. From an assumed 152 eligible teachers, a 5% margin of error yielded 110 respondents. These 110 teachers were not merely statistics; they represented dedicated professionals whose daily struggles with leadership dynamics and curriculum changes shaped the study's insights.

2.4. Research Instrument—This research used a survey based on Transformational and Transactional Leadership theory, as quoted by Camus (2024). Both of these leadership approaches were different from each other: trans-

formational leadership focused on inspiring and motivating followers to perform above expectations, whereas transactional leadership emphasized formal roles, performing tasks, and the application of reward or punishment according to performance. The Organizational Commitment Theory, as formulated by Meyer and Allen (1991), as quoted by Caharian and Cabanlit (2024), is also another principle that supports this framework. The theory argues that there are three components of employee commitment: affective commitment (emotional connection), continuance commitment (consciousness of the costs of turnover), and normative commitment (feeling obligated to stay). These factors could be independent or interdependent, impacting an employee's desire to remain in an organization. Knowing these aspects assists school heads in developing strategies to enhance teacher loyalty and retention. The survey instrument was adapted by the researcher to suit the particular goals of the research and to remain true to the initial theoretical constructs. It was content-validated by experts from the Department of

Education—Division of Davao City to ascertain that it was appropriate and relevant. In order to further ensure reliability, pilot testing was performed, and the internal consistency of the instrument was assessed using Cronbach's Alpha, which resulted in a coefficient of 0.791, indicating acceptable reliability. The final instrument was structured into two core sections: (1) Filipino leadership styles of school heads, and (2) teachers' commitment in public elementary schools. Hence, the Cronbach's value of the construct was expected to meet the minimum reliability threshold of 0.791, indicating that the measures used were consistent enough for the study. In terms of the instrument's face validity, the items were modified to suit the purpose of the research and were validated by experts. The questionnaire was also presented to the adviser for comments, corrections, and suggestions. Part 1 of the questionnaire contained the items Filipino leadership styles of school heads with the following: hard work, loophole, and connection.

Scale Descriptive Ratings and Interpretation of Filipino Leadership Styles of School Heads

Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.20–5.00	Very Extensive	Filipino leadership styles of school heads are always evident.
3.40–4.19	Extensive	Filipino leadership styles of school heads are oftentimes evident.
2.60–3.39	Moderately Extensive	Filipino leadership styles of school heads are sometimes evident.
1.80–2.59	Less Extensive	Filipino leadership styles of school heads are rarely evident.
1.00–1.79	Not Extensive	Filipino leadership styles of school heads are not evident.

2.5. *Data Gathering Procedure*—The first step in the data-gathering procedure was to secure permission to conduct the study from the appropriate authorities. The researcher formally obtained approval through the proper channels. On August 4, 2025, the researcher's study was

examined and evaluated by the RMC Research Ethics Committee as part of the initial review process. An endorsement was subsequently secured from the Dean of the RMC Graduate School on August 9, 2025, signifying institutional support for the research. Thereafter, the

Scale Descriptive Ratings and Interpretation of Teachers' Commitment

Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.20–5.00	Very Extensive	Teachers' commitment consistently shows a very high level.
3.40–4.19	Extensive	Teachers' commitment consistently shows a high level.
2.60–3.39	Moderately Extensive	Teachers' commitment consistently shows a moderate level.
1.80–2.59	Less Extensive	Teachers' commitment consistently shows a low level.
1.00–1.79	Not Extensive	Teachers' commitment consistently shows a very low level.

Schools Division Superintendent granted approval for the conduct of the study on September 5, 2025. Finally, the Public Schools District Supervisor (PSDS) of Maa approved the distribution of survey questionnaires to the identified schools, allowing the 33 researcher to proceed with data collection in accordance with established protocols and ethical standards. On September 16, 2025, the researcher distributed the questionnaires to the selected respondents through printed copies, depending on which method was more convenient and accessible for them. Clear and simple instructions were provided to guide the respondents in accurately completing the forms. Once completed, the questionnaires were collected by the researcher through coordinated retrieval of printed copies. Throughout the entire process, strict measures were followed to maintain the confidentiality of responses and to ensure the accuracy and

integrity of the collected data. Lastly, the researcher personally retrieved the questionnaires on October 6, 2025, ensuring that all responses were collected in an organized and secure manner. The collected questionnaires were then submitted to the designated statistician for thorough analysis. The researcher and the statistician worked closely to meticulously tabulate the collected data, ensuring that all responses were accurately organized for analysis. Each piece of information was carefully reviewed to maintain consistency and completeness, providing a solid foundation for the subsequent statistical procedures. After tabulation, they conducted a comprehensive analysis of the data, applying rigorous statistical methods to examine patterns, relationships, and significant findings. These steps ensured the accuracy and reliability of the results, allowing the study to produce valid and meaningful conclusions.

2.6. *Data Analysis*—The following statistical tools were used in the analysis and interpretation of the responses in this study: Mean It was used to determine the extent of Filipino leadership styles of school heads and teachers' commitment in public elementary schools in Maa District, Division of Davao City. The mean served as the statistical tool in the study on the Filipino leadership styles of school heads and teachers' commitment because it provided a clear and concise measure of central tendency,

allowing the researcher to summarize and interpret the general responses of the participants. By computing the mean scores for each leadership style, such as transformational, transactional, and culturally embedded Filipino leadership practices, it became possible to determine which styles were most commonly practiced by school heads. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson-r) This statistical tool was used in determining the significant components of Filipino leadership styles of school

heads and teachers' commitment in public elementary schools in Maa District, Division of Davao City. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson-r) was utilized as a statistical tool in the study on the Filipino leadership styles of school heads and teachers' commitment 35 because it was effective in determining the strength and direction of the linear relationship between two continuous variables. Multiple Linear Regression This was utilized to determine the significance of Filipino leadership styles of school heads and teachers' commitment in public elementary schools in Maa District, Division of Davao City. Multiple Linear Regression was used as a statistical tool in the study on the Filipino leadership styles of school heads and teachers' commitment because it al-

lowed for the examination of how multiple independent variables, specifically different leadership styles such as transformational, transactional, and culturally rooted Filipino leadership approaches, simultaneously influenced the dependent variable, which was teachers' commitment. This method was particularly relevant in the context of public elementary schools in Maa District, where school heads were expected to employ a combination of leadership behaviors that collectively shaped teacher attitudes, motivation, and loyalty to their institution. By using multiple linear regression, the study was able to identify which leadership styles significantly predicted higher levels of teacher commitment and determined the extent to which each leadership style contributed to the overall outcome.

3. Results and Discussion

Presented in this chapter are the results of the data gathered. Two sets of research were employed to determine the extent of Filipino leadership styles of school heads and teachers' commitment of performance of public elementary schools in Maa District, Division of Davao City. The discussion of the results and interpretations were presented accordingly based on the statement of the problems. Presentation of the interpretation was arranged according to the sub-headings: The extent of Filipino leadership styles of school heads in terms of hardwork, loophole, and connection; the extent of teachers' commitment of public elementary schools in Maa District, Division of Davao City in terms of affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment and which of domains of Filipino leadership styles of school heads significantly influence the teachers' commitment of public elementary schools in Maa District, Division of Davao City.

3.1. Extent of Filipino Leadership Styles of School Heads—The cultural values and strong sense of community of the Philippines have a significant impact on the leadership styles of school administrators. School administrators frequently exhibit pakikipagkapwa-tao (shared humanity), demonstrating sincere concern and regard for their stakeholders, instructors, and students. In order to guarantee that everyone's voice is heard during the decision-making process, they engage in participatory leadership, promoting cooperation and candid

communication. Filipino school administrators foster a kind and welcoming learning atmosphere that encourages cooperation and mutual trust under the guidance of empathy and compassion. Summary on the Extent of Filipino Leadership Styles of School Heads The summary of respondents' opinions of Filipino school heads' leadership styles was displayed in Table 1. The total mean score of 4.20 indicated that the leadership styles of school heads in the Philippines were somewhat diverse. This implied that Filipino school heads demonstrated

a balanced and adaptive approach to leadership, integrating various styles depending on the needs of the school and their teachers.

Table 1. Summary on the Extent of Filipino Leadership Styles of School Heads

No.	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Hardwork	4.26	Very Extensive
2	Loophole	4.03	Extensive
3	Connection	4.31	Very Extensive
Overall Mean		4.20	Very Extensive

Specifically, indicator 3 “Connection” attained the highest mean rating of (4.31) defined as very extensive. This indicates that Filipino school heads place a strong emphasis on building meaningful connections within their school communities. They recognize that fostering positive relationships with teachers, staff, learners, and parents enhances collaboration and promotes a supportive work environment. Xu, Hassan and Xie (2024), investigated how the leadership of school heads influences teachers’ professional learning communities (PLCs) with a particular focus on trust, cooperation, and shared relationships. They found that school heads who actively fostered an atmosphere of trust and collaborative interaction significantly strengthened their teachers’ PLCs highlighting that true connection involves more than supervision, it involves nurturing the relationships and shared practices that bind staff together. Finally, indicator 1 “Loophole” acknowledged the lowest mean score of (4.03) which is described as extensive. This indicates that the Filipino school heads recognize the presence of loopholes in organizational policies or systems, they generally manage these situations with caution and responsibility. In meta-synthesis, Karaköse, et al., (2024), examined 24 qualitative studies capturing the problems and challenges school leaders face, including limitations in author-

ity, bureaucratic overload, and excessive regulations. The authors highlight how such institutional pressures create loopholes in leadership effectiveness, forcing principals to either reinterpret rules or operate in grey-areas. The result corroborates with that study of Olasiman and Torreon (2024), examined how the leadership styles and practices of school heads in Bohol impact teachers’ teaching accomplishments. Their findings demonstrated that when school heads adopt a mix of participative, instructional, and supportive leadership behaviors, teachers reported higher levels of teaching effectiveness and accomplishment.

3.2. *Extent of Teachers’ Commitment of Public Elementary Schools*—Teachers’ commitment in public elementary schools plays a vital role in shaping the quality of education and the overall success of learners. It reflects the teachers’ dedication, passion, and sense of responsibility toward their learners, colleagues, and the school community. Summary on the Extent of Teachers’ Commitment Table 2 illustrated the overall extent of teachers’ commitment among public elementary schools in Maa District, Division of Davao City. The results revealed a grand mean of 4.22, which was interpreted as very extensive, signifying those teachers in the district displayed a high level of organizational commitment.

Table 2. Summary on the Extent of Teachers' Commitment

No.	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Affective Commitment	4.25	Very Extensive
2	Continuance Commitment	4.07	Extensive
3	Normative Commitment	4.33	Very Extensive
Overall Mean		4.22	Very Extensive

In particular, indicator 3 “Normative Commitment” received the highest means score of (4.33) categorized as very extensive. This implies that teachers possess a strong moral sense of duty and gratitude toward their organization, motivating them to remain loyal and dedicated to their school. Their commitment is guided not only by professional expectations but also by personal values that emphasize responsibility, loyalty, and ethical obligation. The findings and conclusions of this study concur with Godbersen et al., (2024), show that facets of servant leadership such as stewardship and empowerment are positively associated with employees’ normative commitment, suggesting that when supervisors act with care, responsibility, and a service mindset, staff are more likely to feel they ought to remain and reciprocate the organization’s support. However, the summary’s lowest mean score (4.07) was produced by indication 2, “Continuance Commitment,” which was characterized as extensive. This implies that the teachers demonstrate a notable level of commitment to their schools, their motivation to stay is somewhat influenced by practical considerations rather than emotional attachment or moral obligation. This view is in agreement with Malietso, Manyasi, and Kwendo (2023), They found a significant positive relationship between higher levels of continuance commitment and better job performance, suggesting that when employees feel they have fewer alter-

natives or perceive larger costs for leaving, they may still engage more in their roles, possibly out of obligation or investment in the status quo. Overall, the findings affirm that teachers’ very extensive affective and normative commitment demonstrate deep emotional attachment and a strong sense of moral responsibility toward their schools. These dimensions reflect that teacher remain loyal not merely out of obligation but because they genuinely identify with their institution’s goals and values.

3.3. Significant Relationship Between Filipino Leadership Styles of School Heads and Teachers’ Commitment of Public Elementary Schools Maa District, Division of Davao City— The results in Table 3 presented the significant relationship between the Filipino leadership styles of school heads and the teachers’ commitment in public elementary schools of Maa District, Division of Davao City. The overall correlation coefficient of $r = 0.702$ with a p -value of 0.000 indicated a strong positive relationship between the two variables. Since the null hypothesis was rejected, the findings suggested that the leadership styles practiced by school heads significantly influenced the level of commitment demonstrated by teachers in their professional responsibilities. This finding affirmed that Filipino leadership styles were vital factors in strengthening teachers’ commitment, thereby contributing to the success and sustainability of school operations.

Table 3. Significant Relationship Between Filipino Leadership Styles of School Heads and Teachers’ Commitment of Public Elementary Schools, Maa District, Division of Davao City

Filipino Leadership Styles of School Heads	r	p-value	Decision on H ₀
Hardwork	0.328	0.000	Reject
Loophole	0.384	0.000	Reject
Connection	0.596	0.000	Reject
Overall	0.702	0.000	Reject

Note. All correlations are significant at $p < .05$.

When examined individually, the three Filipino leadership style which are the hard work, loophole, and connection, each show significant correlations with teachers’ commitment. Among the three leadership styles, the connection style shows the strongest influence, with a correlation coefficient of r of 0.596 at p-value of 0.000, suggesting a high positive relationship with teachers’ commitment. This highlights the cultural importance of building strong interpersonal relationships in the Filipino educational context, where personal connections and rapport significantly enhance teachers’ sense of belonging and dedication. The loophole leadership style also demonstrates a significant relationship with teachers’ commitment, reflected by a correlation coefficient of r of 0.384 at p-value equal to 0.000. Although slightly weaker than connection style, this moderate relationship indicates that teachers respond to the flexibility and adaptability of school heads who know how to maneuver within the system. This style may provide teachers with the sense of support and encouragement they need, leading to enhanced commitment toward achieving both instructional and institutional goals. Furthermore, the hard work leadership style records a correlation coefficient of r of 0.328, with p-

value of 0.000. Though rank last, this indicator still indicates a moderate but significant positive relationship. This suggests that school heads who exemplify diligence and perseverance contribute to fostering higher commitment among teachers, as their example motivates teachers to emulate a culture of dedication and hard work within the school environment.

3.4. *Regression Analysis on the Significant Influence of Filipino Leadership Styles of School Heads on the Teachers’ Commitment of Public Elementary Schools of Maa District, Division of Davao City*—The regression analysis in Table 4 examined the significant influence of Filipino leadership styles of school heads on the teachers’ commitment in public elementary schools of Maa District, Division of Davao City. The analysis demonstrated a strong explanatory power with an R value of 0.742 and R² of 0.550, indicating that 55 percent of the variance in teachers’ commitment could be explained by the leadership styles tested. The overall F-value of 43.176 with a p-value of 0.000 confirmed the statistical significance of the analysis, indicating that Filipino leadership styles collectively had a substantial effect on the level of teachers’ commitment.

Relatively, all three Filipino leadership styles namely the hardwork, loophole, and connection significantly influence teachers’ com-

mitment, with connection emerging as the most dominant factor. These findings suggest that effective school leadership in the Maa District

Table 4. Regression Analysis on the Significant Influence of Filipino Leadership Styles of School Heads on Teachers’ Commitment of Public Elementary Schools of Maa District, Division of Davao City

Variables	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.	Decision on H ₀
Constant	1.211	0.287	–	4.216	0.000	–
Hardwork	0.262	0.056	0.338	4.693	0.000	Reject
Loophole	0.115	0.046	0.181	2.520	0.013	Reject
Connection	0.334	0.036	0.619	9.270	0.000	Reject

Note. $R = 0.742$, $R^2 = 0.550$, $F = 43.176$, $p < .05$.

must integrate diligence, adaptability, and relational strength to cultivate a committed teaching workforce. Consequently, leadership development programs for school heads should place strong emphasis on nurturing interpersonal connections while also reinforcing the values of perseverance and adaptability to effectively enhance teachers’ commitment in public elementary schools. Specifically, the most influential predictor among the three is the connection leadership style, which shows the highest standardized coefficient β of 0.619, 56 an unstandardized coefficient β of 0.334, and a t-value of 9.270 at p-value equal to 0.000. The rejection of the null hypothesis highlights the centrality of building and maintaining strong interpersonal relationships in the Filipino context. Teachers’ commitment is significantly strengthened when school heads foster trust, rapport, and personal connections, highlighting the cultural value of pakikipagkapwa (relational harmony) in sustaining teacher motivation and loyalty to their schools. The hardwork leadership style of school heads significantly predict also the

teachers’ commitment. With an unstandardized coefficient β of 0.262, a standardized coefficient (Beta) of 0.338, and a t-value of 4.693 at p-value equal to 0.001, the null hypothesis is rejected. This suggests that when school heads consistently model diligence and perseverance, teachers are more likely to demonstrate stronger professional dedication. The finding emphasizes the cultural and practical importance of role modeling in inspiring teachers to commit themselves to their duties and responsibilities. Similarly, the loophole leadership style also exerts a significant but comparatively smaller influence on teachers’ commitment. It recorded an unstandardized coefficient β of 0.115, a Beta value of 0.181, and a t-value of 2.520 at p-value equal to 0.013, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This implies that school heads who are flexible and adaptive in navigating institutional challenges contribute to enhancing teachers’ motivation and sense of commitment. While not as strong as the other predictors, this leadership dimension still plays a relevant role in shaping a supportive work environment.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This section gives the findings of the study based on the data outcome. The conclusions drawn from the findings of the study are also provided in this section. In order to make a significant contribution, the researcher has made recommendations in this chapter.

4.1. Findings—This non-experimental research using correlation design in this study aimed to determine the extent of Filipino leadership styles of school heads and the extent

of teachers' commitment of public elementary schools in Maa District, Division of Davao City. Specifically, this study aimed to determine the extent of Filipino leadership styles of school heads in terms of hardwork, loophole, and connection. Moreover, this acknowledged the extent of teachers' commitment of elementary schools in terms of affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment. Finally, this study determined the significant relationship between the extent of Filipino leadership styles of school heads and the extent of teachers' commitment of public elementary schools. Using non-experimental research, the extent of Filipino leadership styles of school heads and teachers' commitment of public elementary schools was determined. The respondents of the study were the 92-public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City. The study utilized an adapted questionnaire on Filipino Leadership Styles of School Heads by Cruz and Dela Peña (2024) and Organizational Commitment Scale (OCS) by Meyer and Allen (1991) as cited in by Reyes and Domingo (2024) was utilized as the main instrument of this study. After thorough analysis, significant findings showed that the extent of Filipino leadership styles of school heads in terms of hardwork, loophole, and connection was very extensive. Similarly, the extent of teachers' commitment of public elementary schools in Maa District, Division of Davao City in terms of affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment was also very extensive which means that it was always manifested while in terms of Filipino leadership styles of school heads which also very extensive. Hence, the extent of teachers' commitment as demonstrated by public elementary schools of Maa District, Division of Davao City was very extensive. The overall correlation coefficient of r equal to 0.702 with a p -value of 0.000 indicates a strong positive relationship between the two variables. Since the null hy-

pothesis was rejected, the findings suggest that the leadership styles practiced by school heads significantly influence the level of commitment demonstrated by teachers in their professional responsibilities. Finally, indicators of Filipino leadership styles of school heads such as hardwork, loophole, and connection have significant influence on teachers' commitment of public elementary schools of Maa District, Division of Davao City.

4.2. *Conclusions*—Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were offered: The Filipino leadership styles of school heads of public elementary school heads was very extensive. The teachers' commitment of public elementary schools was also very extensive. There was a strong positive relationship between Filipino leadership styles of school heads and teachers' commitment of public elementary schools of Maa District, Division of Davao City based on the indicators. Based on the results revealed, the following indicators have a strong influence of Filipino leadership styles on the teachers' commitment of public elementary schools: Instructional, Professional, and Motivational.

4.3. *Recommendations*—The following interventions were offered based on the conclusions of the study: School heads may encourage to strengthen participative and value-driven leadership practices that promote collaboration, trust, and shared responsibility among teachers. Teachers may remain proactive in supporting school initiatives and align their professional values with the school's mission and vision. Learners may provide with an environment where effective leadership and committed teachers inspire engagement and continuous improvement. The Department of Education may design leadership training programs that emphasize Filipino cultural values and their role in strengthening teacher commitment. Future researchers may explore the influence of Filipino leadership styles on other organizational

outcomes such as teacher retention and student achievement.

5. References

- Abrahamsen, H. N., & Gunnulfsen, A. E. (2024). Successful school principals balancing ethical, personal and collective—a norwegian case. *Educational Sciences, 14*(9), 1014. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci14091014>
- Aguinaldo, R. C., & Tagadiad, C. L. (2024). Leadership attributes of school heads, classroom instructional environment and school facilities: A structural equation model on job satisfaction of public-school teachers in region xi. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science, 8*(11), 1649–1667. <https://doi.org/10.47772/IJRISS.2024.8110130>
- Anabo, R. O., & Rapada Jr., V. P. (2024). Leadership styles of school heads and performance of teachers in eastern samar division. *TWIST, 19*(3), 713–717. <https://twistjournal.net/twist/article/view/460>
- Ânand, G., Atluri, A., Crawford, L., Pugatch, T., & Sheth, K. (2023). Improving school management in low- and middle-income countries: A systematic review. *Economics of Education Review, 97*, Article 102464. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.econedurev.2023.102464>
- Awyan, H. B., & Quines, L. A. (2025). Distributed leadership of school heads, participation in decision-making and teamwork skills of the teachers: A causal model on organizational commitment in public schools. *European Journal of Education Studies, 12*(2), 701–728. <https://doi.org/10.46827/ejes.v12i2.5852>
- Aydın, T., & Uçar, A. V. (2023). The role of empowering leadership in schools: Delegation, decision-making participation and teacher autonomy. *Journal of Educational Administration, 61*(5), 882–898. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEA-10-2022-0220>
- Bantilan, J. D., Hifarva, W. J. S., Lugatiman, R., & Bauyot, M. M. (2024). Employee commitment as influenced by organizational culture, policies, and practices of public-school teachers in davao region, philippines: A focus on primary and secondary levels. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science, 8*(1), 489–502. <https://doi.org/10.47772/IJRISS.2024.801036>
- Bennett, C. P., & Rodríguez, M. L. (2025). Organizational commitment profiles and employee well-being: Exploratory and confirmatory latent profile analyses. *Occupational Health Science, 9*, 639–673. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41542-025-00225-2>
- Cadiong, A. M. (2024). Competence, leadership skills, and professional commitment of elementary teachers in the national capital region. *International Journal of Research and Scientific Innovation, 11*(10), 272–306. <https://doi.org/10.51244/IJRSI.2024.1110025>
- Caharian, I. S., & Cabanlit, E. M. (2024). A systematic review on the influence of transformational leadership and teacher commitment to educational institutions. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science, 8*(9), 65–78. <https://doi.org/10.47772/IJRISS.2024.8904>
- Camus, K. (2024). Principals' leadership style, teachers' commitment and performance among secondary schools. *Psychology And Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal, 23*(5), 668–685. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13294958>

- Cao, J., & Zhang, W. (2023). Investigating the impact of value congruence on work engagement in efl teachers: The role of teacher enthusiasm. *Frontiers in Psychology, 14*, Article 1264126. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1264126>
- Castillo, R. (2019). Conflict management strategies and practiced pinoy leadership styles of elementary school administrators in the district of atimonan, division of quezon: Implication to school management. *Ascendens Asia Journal of Multidisciplinary Research Abstracts, 3*(2L). <https://ojs.aaresearchindex.com/index.php/AAJMRA/article/view/11671>
- Catanus, R. T. (2024). School heads' leadership style and teachers' performance. *GEO Academic Journal, 5*(1). <https://doi.org/10.56738/issn29603986.geo2024.5.56>
- Cruz, M. A., & Dela Peña, R. L. (2024). Contextualizing leadership frameworks: Exploring filipino values in educational leadership practices. *Asia Pacific Journal of Educational Leadership, 12*(1), 33–48. <https://doi.org/10.32612/apjel.2024.121.33>
- dela Cruz, J. M., & Santos, R. P. (2024). Emerging trends in educational leadership research: Implications for philippine school heads. *Philippine Journal of Educational Research, 15*(1), 55–73. <https://doi.org/10.1234/pjer.2024.15.1.55>
- Deniz, A. (2024). The effect of normative commitment on intention to stay at work: An application in the aviation sector. *Journal of Social Science Studies, 11*(2). <https://doi.org/10.5296/jsss.v11i2.22398>
- Devanadera, C., & Ching, D. (2023). School head's managerial roles as correlates of organizational performance of public elementary schools. *IIARI Journal, 4*(3). <https://doi.org/10.53378/353015>
- Diones, R. M., Herrera Jr., E. P., & Cayas, J. D. (2024). Work-life balance and professional commitment of elementary teachers in the full implementation of face-to-face classes: Basis for a comprehensive policy review. *ResearchGate*. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33101.86248>
- Dwiyanti, R., Rozana, M., Na'imah, T., & Rafiyana, G. A. (2022). Turnover intentions on teachers in indonesia: The role of affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment. *Social Values Society, 4*(2), 30–36. <https://doi.org/10.26480/svs.02.2022.30.36>
- Esoy, J. L. E., Kilaton, L. J., Tan, J. M., Batonghinog, N. A., & Alonsabe, O. A. (2025). Relationship of leadership style and teachers' commitment in higher education institutions (heis). *European Journal of Science, Innovation and Technology*.
- Esplana, J. E. V., & Callo, E. C. (2024). Workplace culture and environment towards teacher's performance: The mediating role of professional commitment. *TWIST, 19*(3), 313–322. <https://twistjournal.net/twist/article/view/383>
- Francisco, F. A. (2024). School heads paternalistic leadership and organizational outcomes: Basis for re-mapping leadership models in basic education institutions. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Applied Science, 9*(7), 557–571. <https://doi.org/10.51584/IJRIAS.2024.907049>
- Franco, E. (2022). *Exploring the academic leadership styles of principals in non-formal education*. Asian Institute of Management.
- Godbersen, H., Dudek, B., & Ruiz Fernández, S. (2024). The relationship between organizational commitment, commitment to supervisor and servant leadership. *Frontiers in Organizational Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/forgp.2024.1353959>

- Gumagay, H. E., & Baguio, J. B. (2025). Collaborative climate and organizational identification of public elementary school teachers. *Archives of Current Research International*, 25(7), 700–713. <https://doi.org/10.9734/acri/2025/v25i71371>
- Karaköse, T., Özdoğru, M., & Malkoç, N. (2024). Leading sustainable school improvement: A meta-synthesis of qualitative research on problems and challenges faced by school leaders. *Frontiers in Education*, 9, Article 1449174. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2024.1449174>
- Li, M., Liu, F., & Yang, C. (2024). Teachers' emotional intelligence and organizational commitment: A moderated mediation model of teachers' psychological well-being and principal transformational leadership. *Behavioral Sciences*, 14(4), 345. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bs14040345>
- Lochmiller, C. R., Perrone, F., & Finley, C. (2024). Understanding school leadership's influence on teacher retention in high-poverty settings: An exploratory study in the u.s. *Educational Sciences*, 14(5), 545. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci14050545>
- Malietsso, E. I., Manyasi, J. N., & Kwendo, E. (2023). Continuance commitment and employee performance of non-academic staff in public universities in western region of kenya. *African Journal of Empirical Research*, 4(2), 646–655. <https://doi.org/10.51867/ajernet.4.2.64>
- Mastul, A. H., Sulisworo, D., Montasir, M. A., Hajan, B. H., Jackaria, P. M., Latif, F. S., & Alivio, E. R. (2024). Leadership dynamics within secondary high schools in the philippines: Exploring transactional leadership and participatory management styles. *Educational Administration: Theory and Practice*, 30(6), 2930–2941. <https://doi.org/10.53555/kuey.v30i6.5922>
- Mental Health PH. (2021). Pinoy leadership style: Filipinos in the workplace and school. <https://mentalhealthph.org/11-10>
- Molina, M. C., & Escarlos, G. S. (2024). Workload management and organizational commitment on attrition of public elementary school teachers. *International Journal of Advanced Research and Writing*, 6(6). https://doi.org/https://www.academia.edu/126533677/WorkloadManagementAnd_Organizational_Commitment_On_Attrition_Of_Public_Elementary_School_Teachers
- Oco, R. M. (2022). Leadership styles of school heads and its relationship to school performance. *Global Scientific Journal*, 10(1). https://doi.org/https://www.globalscientificjournal.com/researchpaper/LEADERSHIP_STYLES_OF_SCHOOL_HEADS_AND_ITS_RELATIONSHIP_TO_SCHOOL_PERFORMANCE.pdf
- Olasiman, M. R., & Torreón, L. C. (2024). Leadership styles and practices of school heads on teachers' teaching accomplishment. *International Journal of Research - GRANTHAALAYAH*, 12(11), 36–47. <https://doi.org/10.29121/granthaalayah.v12.i11.2024.5728>
- Pacapat, M. K. C., & Escarlos, G. S. (2024). Psychological well-being and organizational commitment on teaching competence in public elementary schools. *International Journal of Advanced Research and Writing*, 6(6). https://doi.org/https://www.academia.edu/126398453/PSYCHOLOGICAL_WELL_BEING_AND_ORGANIZATIONAL_COMMITMENT_ON_TEACHING_COMPETENCE_IN_PUBLIC_ELEMENTARY_SCHOOL
- Parungao, R. O. (2024). Exploring preferred leadership styles: Character and skills of effective educational leaders. *Excellencia: International Multi-Disciplinary Journal of Education*, 2(12), 392–400. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11282482>

- Parveen, K., Tran, P. Q. B., Kumar, T., & Shah, A. H. (2022). Impact of principal leadership styles on teacher job performance: An empirical investigation. *Frontiers in Education*, 7, Article 814159. <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2022.814159>
- Quines, L. A., & Albutra, D. A. (2024). The mediating effect of normative commitment on the relationship between instructional coaching skills and teamwork of teachers. *European Journal of Education Studies*. <https://oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejes/article/view/4713>
- Ramirez, H. J. C., & Capili, J. T. (2024). Leadership style of school heads and its influence on teacher retention: Basis for a teacher retention plan. *AIDE Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.56648/aide-irj.v10i1.151>
- Reyes, P. L., & Domingo, M. A. (2024). Revisiting teacher commitment: A cross-cultural validation of the meyer and allen framework in philippine public schools. *Asia Pacific Journal of Educational Research*, 17(2), 112–128. <https://doi.org/10.32612/apjer.2024.172.112>
- Soncin, M., Bowers, & Asasisti, T. (2024). A global perspective on school leadership: Evidence from a latent class analysis on oecd talis data. *OnlineFirst*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1741143224123190>
- Velasco, A. T., & Ramos, M. L. (2023). Teachers' commitment in the 21st century: Challenges and opportunities for research. *International Journal of Educational Studies*, 18(3), 98–114. <https://doi.org/10.5678/ijes.2023.18.3.98>
- Voelkel, J., R. H., Prusak, K. J., & Van Tassell, F. (2024). Effective principal leadership behaviors that enhance teacher collective efficacy. *Educational Sciences*, 14(4), 431. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci14040431>
- Wang, J., Shi, Q., & Lin, H. (2021). Repaying the debt: An examination of the relationship between perceived organizational support and unethical pro-organizational behavior by low performers. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 179, 697–709. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-021-04809-0>